

Evaluating the Effectiveness of the Mining Android Sandbox (MAS) Approach for Malicious App Detection in Large Datasets

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Abstract. The widespread use of smartphones, particularly Android devices, has raised significant security concerns. The Mining Android Sandbox (MAS) approach has been used to identify malicious behavior in repackaged Android applications, but its effectiveness has been questioned due to the limited size of previous datasets. This paper presents a replication study with a significantly larger dataset comprising 4,076 pairs of original and repackaged apps, covering a wider variety of Android malware families. Contrary to previous findings, we observe a sharp decline in the MAS approach’s accuracy, with the F1-score dropping from 0.89 to 0.54. Our analysis reveals that the higher representation of certain malware families in the larger dataset contributes to the MAS approach’s reduced accuracy. The study highlights the limitations of the MAS approach when scaled and emphasizes the need for integrating additional techniques to enhance malware detection across diverse app variants.

1 Introduction

Mobile technologies like smartphones and tablets have become fundamental to the way we function as a society. Almost two-thirds of the world population uses mobile technologies [1,2], with the Android Platform dominating this market and accounting for more than 70% of the *mobile market share*, with almost 2.5 million Android applications available on the Google Play Store, in June 2023 [3]. As popularity rises, so does the risk of potential attacks, prompting collaborative efforts from both academia and industry to design and develop new techniques for identifying malicious behavior or vulnerable code in Android apps [4].

For instance, one popular class of Android malware is based on repackaging apps [5,6] where a benign version of an app is infected with malicious code, e.g., to broadcast sensitive information to a private server [7], and subsequently shared with users using even official app stores. The Mining Android Sandbox approach () was initially designed to construct sandboxes based on exploratory calls to sensitive APIs [8]. However, it has also proven effective in detecting Android repackaged malware. The operates in two distinct phases. In the first phase (exploratory phase), it utilizes automated test case generation tools to abstract the behavior of an app, focusing on calls to sensitive APIs (Application

Programming Interfaces). Subsequently, during the normal executions of the app, the generated sandbox blocks any calls to sensitive APIs not observed during the exploratory phase.

Prior studies [5,9] have investigated the application of the MAS approach in detecting potential malicious behavior in repackaged apps. These studies have also conducted comparisons of the approach’s performance by employing different test case generation tools during the exploratory phase, including Monkey [10], DroidBot [11], and Droidmate [12]. These studies provide evidence that DroidBot surpasses other test generation tools, uncovering a larger number of potential malicious behaviors. But these previous studies have two main limitations. First, they use a small dataset of malware comprising only pairs of original/repackaged versions of an app—compromising external validity. Second, their assessments do not investigate the impact of relevant features of the repackaged apps on the accuracy of the for malware classification, including (a) whether or not the repackaged version is a malware, (b) the similarity between the original and the repackaged versions of an app, and (c) the malware family (e.g., gappusin, kuguo, dowgin, etc.) when the repackaged version of an app is a malware. This limitations compromise a full understanding of the performance. We present more details about the and related work in Section 2.

To understand the impact of these issues on results already published in the literature, in this paper we reconsider the accuracy of the based on DroidBot [11]—as we mentioned, the test case generation tool that, according to the literature, leads to the most accurate Android sandbox, regarding malware identification. Compared to previous studies [5,13], we use a curated dataset of app pairs (original/repackaged versions) that is, in terms of magnitude, larger than the previously used dataset (it contains pairs of original/repackaged apps). We detail our datasets and the procedures we follow for data collection and data analysis in Section 3.

Negative results. Our study reveals a significantly lower accuracy (of) of the in comparison to what has been reported before (of). Since an accuracy of is clearly unsatisfactory for a trustworthy malware classification technique, we conduct a set of experiments to understand the reasons for the lower accuracy in our larger dataset. Our further assessments reveal that the fails to correctly classify most samples from a specific set of malware families, particularly those from the family (a particular class of adware that frequently appears in repackaged apps). Out of the total of samples within this family in our large dataset, the failed to correctly classify samples as malware. Accordingly, these families are responsible for substantially reducing the recall of the . We detail the results of our experiments in Section 4.

We also discuss the implications and possible threats to the validity of our study in Section 5 and present some final remarks in Section 6. The main artifacts we produced during this research are available in the paper repository.

2 Background and Related Work

There are many tools that favor developers to reverse engineering the Android bytecode language [14]. For this reason, software developers can easily decompile trustworthy apps, modify their contents by inserting malicious code, repackage them with malicious payloads, and re-publish them in app stores, including official ones like the Google Play Store. It is well-known that repackaged Android apps can leverage the popularity of real apps to increase their propagation and spread malware [7]. As an example, in 2016 a repackaged version of the famous Pokémon Go app was discovered less than 72 hours after the game was officially released in the United States, Australia, and New Zealand [7]. The repackaged version, originated from an unofficial app store, gained full control over the victim’s phone, obtaining access to main functions such as the phonebook, audio recorder, and camera.

Repackaging has been raised as a noteworthy security concern in Android ecosystem by stakeholders in the app development industry and researchers [15]. Indeed, there are reports claiming that about 25% of Google Play Store app content correspond to repackaged apps [16]. Nevertheless, all the workload to detect and remove malware from markets by the stores (official and non-official ones), have not been accurate enough to address the problem. As a result, repackaged Android apps threaten security and privacy of unsuspecting Android app users, beyond compromising the copyright of the original developers [17]. Aiming at mitigating the threat of malicious code injection in repackaged apps, several techniques based on both static and dynamic analysis of Android apps have been proposed, including the for malware classification [8,5].

2.1 Mining Android Sandboxes

A *sandbox* is a well-known mechanism to secure a system and forbid a software component from accessing resources without appropriate permissions. Sandboxes have also been used to build an isolated environment within which applications cannot affect other programs, the network, or other device data [18]. The idea of using sandboxes emerged from the need to test unsafe software, possible malware, without worrying about the integrity of the device under test [19], shielding the operating system from security issues. To this end, a sandbox environment should have the minimum requirements to run the program, and make sure it will never assign the program more privileges than it should have, respecting the *least privilege* principle. Within the Android ecosystem, sandbox approaches ensure the principle of the *least privilege* by preventing apps from having direct access to resources like device hardware (e.g., GPS, Camera), or sensitive data from other apps. Access to sensitive data like contact list or resources are granted through specific APIs, known as sensitive APIs, which are managed by the coarse-grained Android permissions system [20].

The [8] aims at automatically building a sandbox through dynamic analysis (i.e., using automatic test generation tools). The main idea is to grant permissions to an app based on its calls to sensitive APIs. Thus, sandboxes build upon

these calls to create safety rules and then block future calls to other sensitive resources, which diverge from those found in the first exploratory phase. Using the Droidmate test generation tool [21], Jamrozik et al. proposed a full-fledged implementation of the , named Boxmate [8]. Boxmate records the occurrences of calls to sensitive APIs and, optionally, the UI events (e.g., a button click) that trigger these calls. Therefore, it is possible to configure Boxmate to record events associated with each sensitive call as tuples (event, API), instead of recording just the set of calls to sensitive APIs. Jamrozik et al. argue that, in this way, Boxmate generates finer grain results, which might improve the accuracy of the —even with the presence of reflection, a feature commonly used in malicious apps [22].

In fact, the can be implemented using a mix of static and dynamic analysis. In the first phase, one can instrument an Android app to log any call to the Android sensitive methods. After that, one can execute a test case generation tool (such as DroidMate, DroidBot, or Monkey) to explore the app behavior at runtime, while the calls to sensitive APIs are recorded. This set of calls to sensitive APIs is then used to configure the sandbox. The general suggests that the more efficient the test generation tool (for instance, in terms of code coverage), the more accurate would be the resulting sandbox.

2.2 Mining Android Sandbox for Malware Classification

Besides being used to generate Android sandboxes, the is also effective to detect if a repackaged version of an Android app contains malicious behavior [5]. In this scenario, the *effectiveness* of the approach is estimated in terms of the accuracy in which malicious behavior is correctly identified in the repackaged version of the apps.

The for malware classification typically works as follows. In a first step (**instrumentation phase**), a tool instruments the code of the apps (both original and repackaged versions) to collect relevant information during the apps execution in later stages. Then, in a second step (**exploration phase**), the collects a set S_1 with all calls to sensitive APIs the original version of an app executes while running a test case generator tool (like DroidBot). In the third step (**exploitation phase**), the (a) collects a set S_2 with all calls to sensitive APIs the repackaged version of an app executes while running a test case generator tool and then (b) computes the set $S = S_2 \setminus S_1$ and checks whether S is empty or not. The classifies the repackaged version as a malware whenever $|S| > 0$.

Previous research works reported the results of empirical studies that aim to investigate the effectiveness of the for malware classification [5,13]. For instance, Bao et al. found that, in general, the sandboxes constructed using test generation tools classify at least 66% of repackaged apps as malware in a dataset comprising 102 pairs of apps (original/repackaged versions) [5]. Actually, the mentioned work performed two studies: one pilot study involving a dataset of 10 pairs of apps (**SmallE**), in which the authors executed each test case generation tools for one hour; and a larger experiment (**LargeE**) involving 102 pairs of apps in which the authors executed the test case generation tools for one minute [5].

Here we replicate their larger experiment. The authors also presented that, among five test generation tools used, DroidBot [11] leads to the most effective sandbox. Le et al. extend the for malware classification with additional verification, such as the values of the actual parameters used in the calls to sensitive APIs [6], while Costa et al. [9] investigated the impact of static analysis to complement the accuracy of the for malware classification. Their study reports that DroidFax [23], the static analysis infrastructure used in [5], classifies as malware almost half of the repackaged apps.

2.3 Android Malware Classification - State-of-the-art

The field of malware detection for the Android platform is fertile, with a significant number of secondary studies already published [24,25,26,27]. In general, malware detection techniques are divided into static detection, dynamic detection, and hybrid detection [28]. Several studies have also conducted surveys on malware detection techniques and presented a review of them [29,30,31]. For instance, M. Odusami et al. [31] discuss various static analyses approaches that have been used in the literature to identify malicious behavior in Android apps. The authors present some works with permission and signature-based malware detection systems. They highlight that both approaches have a low false positive rate; however, they are very ineffective in detecting new malware. Although they could reveal possible malicious behaviors, the authors discuss several limitations of these approaches, as they are limited regarding code obfuscation and dynamic code loading.

The literature also presents surveys based on dynamic analysis, where malicious behavior is analyzed at runtime, exposing risks that are not detected by static analysis. As a malicious app “is alive”, dynamic analysis adds another degree of analysis since it observes how Android apps interacts with the environment. However, if applied inappropriately, it may provide limited code coverage, which can be improved by repeated executions. Therefore, the time cost and computation resources of dynamic analysis are high when compared with static analysis. K. Tam et al. [30] presented several dynamic analysis studies based on different Android architectural layers, like Hardware, Network, and User, and their interactions. The survey also exposed that dynamic analysis can be performed in emulator environments, real devices, or both. The authors discuss that the choice of environments is an important issue for analysis, as there are malware families that can detect emulated environments and do not exhibit malicious behaviors [32]. Finally, K. Tam et al. also exposed some works based on hybrid malware detectors and claim that these methods can increase code coverage and robustness, taking advantage of the best of each technique to find malicious behaviors.

Several studies have also explored Android malware detection approaches based on machine learning techniques, employing both static and dynamic analyses to extract features and train systems [29]. Most of these approaches have demonstrated high accuracy (above 90%), effectively detecting previously unseen malware families with low false positives rate [33]. However, some studies have

pointed out various limitations associated with machine learning approaches for Android malware classification. In their work, K. Liu et al [29] highlighted challenges related to machine learning techniques, identifying several factors that could lead to biased results, such as the quality of the sample set. The authors argue that samples of poor quality, with a non-representative size or outdated samples, may yield promising results in experimental settings but might not perform similarly in a real environment [34]. Another critical aspect is the quality of the extracted feature dataset. The efficacy of machine learning approaches heavily relies on the selection of correct features and their extraction methods, particularly dynamic features. Moreover, in addition to the computational costs involved, other studies [35,36] have indicated that machine learning approaches exhibit weaknesses when dealing with malicious apps that alter their behavior to mislead learning algorithms, which may restricts their applicability in real-world scenarios.

3 Experimental Setup

Our goal is to build an in-depth understanding about the performance of the for detecting malware. To this end, we replicate previous studies using a dataset of repackaged apps that is an order of magnitude larger than the datasets used before [5,9]. Accordingly, we investigate the following research questions:

[(RQ1)]

In this section, we describe our study settings. First, we present the procedures we use to create our datasets (Section 3.1). Then, we describe the data collection and data analysis procedures (Sections 3.2 and 3.3).

3.1 Malware Dataset

To address our research questions, we curated a dataset designed to meet two primary requirements. Firstly, it should encompass a comprehensive and current selection of Android repackaged apps, spanning a diverse range of malware families for representativeness. Secondly, our dataset should be appropriately labeled, ensuring that key attributes of each app, such as similarity and malware family, are known in advance.

Procedures for Building the Dataset We curate our dataset in three main phases. First, we use two repositories of repackaged Android apps ([7] and [37]) to build the dataset we use in our research. was curated using automatic procedures that extract repackaged apps from the Androzoo repository [38]. It comprises a total of 18,073 apps, from which 2,776 are original versions of an app and the remaining ones are repackaged versions. contains a total of 15,297 pairs of original and repackaged Android apps—many repackaged versions of the same original app may coexist within the dataset. is the leading dataset used in Android repackaged research [15], even though it only contains packages built

up until 2018. For this reason, we decided to include samples from the dataset that were built after 2018 in our research. Nonetheless, unlike RePack, lacks information about the original apps, leading us to follow an existing heuristic [7] to identify the original versions of the repackaged apps in , leading to a sample from the dataset that contains 1,190 pairs (original/repackaged) of apps—all pairs satisfying our constraint of being built after 2018. Altogether, our initial dataset contains a total of 16,487 pairs of apps.

Secondly, during the execution of our experiments, we encountered recurrent issues with many samples in our initial dataset. Many of these issues arose during the process of instrumenting the apps using DroidFux [23]. Other problems occurred after the execution of the apps in the Android emulator, while analysing the apps and the execution logs . More specifically, we encountered failures while instrumenting 919 original apps from our initial dataset, including both and . After removing these original apps from our dataset, we were left with a total of 5,875 pairs (original/repackaged) of apps. Among these pairs, 430 repackaged apps could not be instrumented. A total of 586 failures occurred while analysing the original or repackaged version of the apps and their execution logs, resulting in a dataset containing a total of 4,742 pairs. Finally, we were not able to install five apps in the version of the Android emulator (API level 28) we used in our research. Compared to our experience building our dataset, a larger percentage of failures have been reported in previous research [5].

Third, we queried the repository to identify original versions of apps labeled as malware. Samples with such labels were excluded from our dataset, as the assumes that the original version of an app is not malware (otherwise, the repackaged versions might also exhibit malicious behavior). is a widely recognized tool that scans software assets, including Android apps, using over 60 antivirus engines [15]. Thus, we excluded 661 samples from our dataset that do not satisfy this constraint.

In the end, we are left with our final dataset (hereafter) of apps which we use in our study. To bring evidence that we were able to reproduce the results of previous research, we also consider in our research a small dataset () used in the original studies [5,9].

Features of the Datasets We queried the repository to find out which repackaged apps in our dataset have been indeed labeled as a malware. According to , in the (102 pairs), 69 of the repackaged apps (67.64%) have been identified as a malware by at least two . Here we only consider that a repackaged version of an app is a malware if reports that at least two identify a malicious behavior within the asset. This is in accordance with previous research [39,15]. Considering the , at least two security engines identified out of the repackaged apps as malware (%). In Section 5, we show that our results remain consistent across three additional scenarios: when classifying a repackaged version of an app as malware if at least one, five, or ten engines flag it as malicious.

Classifying malware into different categories is a common practice. For instance, Android malware can be classified into categories like riskware, trojan,

adware, etc. Each category might be further specialized in several malware families, depending of its characteristics and attack strategy—e.g., steal network info (IP, DNS, WiFi), collect phone info, collect user contacts, send/receive SMS, and so on [40]. According to the [41], the malware samples in the come from 17 different families—most of them from the Kuguo (49.27%) and Dowgin (17.39%) families. Our , besides a large sample of repackaged apps (in total), comprises 116 families of malware we collected using the —most of them from the Gapusin (46.18%) family. Despite being flagged as malicious by at least two security engine, unfortunately cannot correctly identify the family of 253 samples from our .

We also characterize our dataset according to the similarity between the original and repackaged versions of the apps, using the SimiDroid tool [42]. SimiDroid quantifies the similarity based on (a) the methods that are either identical or similar in both versions of the apps (original and repackaged versions), (b) methods that only appear in the repackaged version of the apps (new methods), and (c) methods that only appear in the original version of the apps (deleted methods). Our has an average similarity score of (90.39)%, with the following distribution: 87 of app pairs have a similarity score of less than 25%, 49 of app pairs between 25% and 50%, 353 of the apps between 50% and 75%, and 3,587 of the apps with more than 75%. The presents a similarity index average of (89.41%).

After executing our experiments, we identified the most frequently abused sensitive APIs called by the repackaged version of our samples. We observed that upon execution of all samples from our dataset (and), malicious app versions injected 133 distinct methods from sensitive APIs (according to the AppGuard [43] security framework). Malicious code often exploits these APIs to compromise system security and access sensitive data. Table 1 presents a list of the 10 most frequently injected methods from sensitive APIs found in the samples of repackaged versions of the apps.

It is important to highlight that our samples come from different Android app stores. Most of our repackaged apps come from a non-official Android app store, Anzhi [44]. However, some repackaged apps also come from the official Android app store, Google Play.

3.2 Data Collection Procedures

We take advantage of the DroidXP infrastructure [13] for data collection. DroidXP allows researchers to compare test case generation tools in terms of malicious app behaviors identification, using the . Although the comparison of test case generation tools is not the goal of this paper, DroidXP was still useful for automating the following steps of our study.

[S1]**Instrumentation:** In the first step, we configure DroidXP to instrument all pairs of apps in our datasets. Here, we instrument both versions of the apps (as APK files) to collect relevant information during their execution. Under the hood, DroidXP leverages DroidFux to instrument the apps and collect static information about them. To improve the performance across multiple executions, this phase executes only once for each version of the

Table 1. Sensitive APIs Frequently Used in Repackaged Apps. The *Occurrences* column indicates the number of distinct repackaged apps introducing calls to sensitive methods.

Sensitive API Method	Occurrences
android.telephony.TelephonyManager: int getPhoneType()	311
android.telephony.TelephonyManager: String getNetworkOperatorName()	297
android.location.LocationManager: String getBestProvider(Criteria, boolean)	292
android.telephony.TelephonyManager: int getSimState()	284
java.lang.reflect.Field: Object get(Object)	277
android.net.NetworkInfo: String getTypeName()	271
android.database.sqlite.SQLiteDatabase: Cursor query(String, String[], ...)	270
java.lang.reflect.Field: int getInt(Object)	250
android.net.wifi.WifiInfo: String getMacAddress()	238
android.telephony.TelephonyManager: String getNetworkOperator()	237

apps in our dataset. **Execution:** In this step, DroidXP first installs the (instrumented) version of the APK files in the Android emulator we use in our experiment (API 28) and then starts a test case generation tool for executing both app versions (original and repackaged). We execute the apps via DroidBot [11], mostly because previous research works report the best accuracy of the sandboxes built using the and the DroidBot as test case generation tool. Since previous research also indicated that DroidBot’s coverage reaches near-maximum within one minute, we run each app for three minutes, and for three times, to mitigate the randomness involved in test case generation tools. To also ensure that each execution gets the benefit of running on a fresh Android instance without biases that could stem out of history, DroidXP wipes out all data stored on the emulator that has been collected from previous executions. **Data Collection:** After the execution of the instrumented apps, once again, DroidXP leverages DroidFax, this time to collect all relevant information (such as calls to sensitive APIs, test coverage metrics, and so on). We use this information to analyze the performance of the for detecting malicious behavior.

The overall architecture of the is represented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The overall architecture of the

3.3 Data Analysis Procedures

We consider that a test generation tool, in our case, DroidBot, builds a sandbox that labels a repackaged version of an app as a malware if there is at least one call to a sensitive APIs that (a) was observed while executing the repackaged version of the app and that (b) was not observed while executing the original version of the same app. If the set of sensitive methods that only the repackaged version of an app calls is empty, we conclude that the sandbox does not label the repackaged version of an app as a malware. The set of sensitive APIs we use was defined in the AppGuard framework [43], which was based on the mapping from sensitive APIs to permissions proposed by Song et al. [45]. We triangulate the results of the classification with the outputs of , which might lead to one of the following situations:

- 3. **True Positive (TP)**. The labels a repackaged version as a malware and, according to , at least two label the asset as a malware.
- **True Negative (TN)**. The does not label a repackaged version as a malware and, according to , at most one labels the asset as a malware.
- **False Positive (FP)**. The labels a repackaged version as a malware and, according to , at most one labels the asset as a malware.
- **False Negative (FN)**. The does not label a repackaged version as a malware, and according to , at least two label the asset as a malware.

In Section 4 we compute *Precision*, *Recall*, and *F-measure* (F_1) from the number of true-positives, false-positives, and false-negatives (using standard formulae). We use basic statistics (average, median, standard deviation) to identify the accuracy of the for malware classification, using both datasets—i.e., the with 102 pairs of apps and with pairs. We use the Spearman Correlation [46] method and Logistic Regression [47] to understand the strengths of the associations between the similarity index between the original and the repackaged versions of a malware with the accuracy—that is, if the approach was able to correctly classify an asset as malware. We also use existing tools to reverse engineer a sample of repackaged apps in order to better understand the (lack of) accuracy of the .

4 Results

In this section, we detail the findings of our study. We remind the reader that our main goal with this study is to better understand the strengths and limitations of the for malware detection using the state-of-the-art test case generation tool (DroidBot). We explore the results of our research using two datasets: the (app pairs), and (pairs).

4.1 Exploratory Data Analysis of Accuracy

. Considering the (102 apps), the for malware detection classifies a total of 69 repackaged versions as malware (67.64%). This result is close to what Bao et al. reported [5]. That is, in their original paper, the using DroidBot classifies 66.66% of the repackaged version of the apps as malware [5]. This result confirms that we were able to reproduce the findings of the original study using our implementation of the .

1We were able to reproduce the results of existing research using our implementation of the , achieving a malware classification in the close to what has been reported in previous studies.

In the previous studies [5,9], the authors assume that all repackaged versions contain a malicious behavior. For this reason, the authors do not explore accuracy metrics (such as Precision, Recall, and F-measure (F_1))—all repackaged apps labeled as malware are considered true positives in the previous studies. As we mentioned, in this paper we take advantage of to label our dataset and build a ground truth: In our datasets, we classify a repackaged version of an app as malware if, according to our query results, at least two security engines identify malicious behavior in the asset. This decision aligns with existing recommendations [39,15]). The first row of Table 2 shows that the achieves an accuracy of 0.89 when considering the . Nonetheless, the fails to correctly classify seven assets as malware on the (FN column, first row of Table 2), and wrongly labeled the repackaged version of seven apps as malware (FP column).

. Surprisingly, considering our complete dataset (apps), the labels a total of 1,395 repackaged apps as malware (34.22% of the total number of repackaged apps)—for which the repackaged version calls at least one additional sensitive

Table 2. Accuracy of the in both datasets.

Dataset	TP	FP	FN	Precision	Recall	F_1
(102)	62	7	7	0.89	0.89	0.89
(4,076)	1,175	220	1,720	0.84	0.40	0.54

API. Our analysis also reveals a **negative result** related to the accuracy of the approach: here, the accuracy is much lower in comparison to what we reported for the (see the second row of Table 2): F_1 dropping from to . This result indicates that, when considering a large dataset, the accuracy of the using DroidBot drops significantly.

2 The for malware detection leads to a substantially lower performance on the (pairs of apps), dropping the from 0.89 to in comparison to what we observed in the .

Therefore, the resulting sandbox we generate using DroidBot suffers from a significantly low accuracy rate when considering a large dataset. This is shown in the second row of Table 2. The negative performance of the in the encouraged us to endorse efforts aimed at identifying potential reasons for this phenomenon and motivate the research questions RQ2 and RQ3.

4.2 Assessment Based on

Figure 2 shows the distribution over the two datasets we use in our research (the and the). Recall that the measures how similar the original and repackaged versions of an app are. The SmallDS exhibits an average of 0.89 (with a median of 0.99 and standard deviation of 0.25), whereas the complete dataset averages a of 0.90 (with a median of 0.98 and standard deviation of 0.18).

The average of the is 0.89 (median of 0.99 and sd of 0.25); while the average of the complete dataset is 0.90 (median of 0.98 and sd of 0.18).

In this section we investigate how the influences the accuracy of the . We employ Logistic Regression to quantify the relationship between them. For this analysis, instances of true negatives (i.e., cases where the repackaged version is benign according to and the correctly labels it as benign) are excluded. As such, we test the following null hypothesis:

H_0 does not influence the accuracy of the for malware detection.

The results of the logistic regression suggest that we should reject our null hypothesis (p -value = $2.22 \cdot 10^{-16}$). This finding indicates that the accuracy of the is influenced by the similarity between the original and repackaged versions of an app.

3There is an association between the and the performance, which means that the similarity between the original and repackaged versions of an app can explain the performance of the for malware classification.

To clarify the lack of association between and correctness, we use the *K-Means* algorithm to split the into ten clusters—according to the . We then estimate the percentage of correct classifications for each cluster, as we show in

Fig. 2. of the malware samples in the small and complete datasets. The boxplots in the figure do not show outliers.

Table 3. Note that the achieves the highest percentage of correct classification (70.40%) for the third cluster ($cId = 3$), which presents an average of (0.67). Nonetheless, the cluster $cId = 10$, with larger number of samples (1,248) and (0.99), presents a percentage of correct classifications of 26.68%. We can observe that as the average similarity rate decreases, there is a tendency toward greater accuracy in the . Hence, the average similarity score could explain the poor performance of the on the , especially considering that most samples exhibit a high average similarity of 0.99.

4.3 Assessment Based on Malware Family

As we discussed in the previous section, the similarity assessment partially explains the low performance of the on the . Since the covers a wide range of malware families, we investigate the hypothesis that the diversity of malware families in the also contributes to the poor performance of the on the . Indeed, in the , we identified a total of 116 malware families, though the most frequent ones are (samples), revmob (207 samples), dowgin (183 samples) and *airpush* (120 samples). Together, they account for 63.79% of the repackaged apps in our labeled as malware according to .

This family distribution in the is different from the family distribution in the —where the families kuguo (34 samples), dowgin (12 samples), and youmi (5

Table 3. Characteristics of the clusters. Note there is a specific pattern associating the percentage of correct answers with the . For this analysis, we removed the true negatives in our dataset.

cId	Samples	Correct Answers	%
1	0.09	93	46 49.46
2	0.55	175	106 60.57
3	0.67	125	88 70.40
4	0.79	165	90 54.55
5	0.87	261	77 29.50
6	0.90	230	121 52.61
7	0.94	141	46 32.62
8	0.97	140	59 42.14
9	0.98	398	95 23.87
10	0.99	1248	333 26.68

samples) account for 73.91% of the families considering the 69 repackaged apps labels as malware in the . Most important, in the , there is just one sample from the family and no sample from revmob family, two of the most frequent families in our . This observation leads us to the question: how does the perform when considering only samples from the and revmob families?

The confusion matrix of Table 4 summarizes the accuracy assessment of the considering only the and revmob samples in the . Note that classifies as malware all repackaged versions in the and revmob family. It is worth noting that the failed to correctly classify 1,170 (87.5%) samples of as malware. Similarly, 92 samples (44.44%) from revmov were not classified as malware. Furthermore, if we exclude the and revmov samples from the , the recall of the increases to 0.72, which, although improved, remains relatively low compared to the original studies.

Table 4. Confusion matrix of the when considering only the samples from the and revmob family in the .

Actual Condition	Predicted Condition	
	Benign	Malware
Benign (0)	TN (0)	FP (0)
Gappusin ()	FN ()	TP (167)
Revmob (207)	FN (92)	TP (115)

4The fails to correctly identify 87.50% of the samples from the family and 44.44% of the samples from the revmob as malware. Just like the Similarity Score, the presence of some malware families with a high false negative rate also influences the low recall of the in the

We further analyze the samples from the and malware families in our dataset, given their relevance to the negative results presented in our paper. First, we

examined the of the samples. Figure 3 shows a histogram of the for both families. Notably, most of the repackaged versions are quite similar to the original versions, with an average of 0.94, a median of 0.99, and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.16 for the family. For the family, the average is 0.81, the median is 0.91, and the SD is 0.26.

We also reverse-engineered samples from both families. Due to the significant effort required for reverse engineering, we limited our analysis to a sample of 30 and 30 malware samples, using the and median are 0.99 and 0.90 for the and families, respectively. Table 5 and Table 6 summarize the outputs of `SimiDroid` for these samples.

Regarding the malware, the similarity assessment of this sample of 30 apps reveals a few modification patterns when comparing the original and the repackaged versions. First, no instance in this sample dataset modifies the Android Manifest file to require additional permissions, for instance. In most cases, the repackaged version just changes the Manifest file to modify either the package name or the main activity name. Moreover, 29 out of the 30 samples in this dataset **modifies** the method `void onReceive(Context, Intent)` of the class `com.games.AdReceiver`. Although the results of the decompilation process are difficult to understand in full (due to code obfuscation), the goal of this modification is to change the behavior of the benign version, so that it can download a different version of the `data.apk` asset. Figure 4 shows the code pattern of the `onReceive` method present in the samples. This modification typically uses a new method (`public void a(Context)`) the repackaged versions often introduce into the same class (`AdReceiver`). Since there is no extra call to sensitive APIs, the fails to label the samples correctly.

Our assessment also reveals recurrent modification patterns that **delete** methods in the repackaged version of the apps. For instance, 20 repackaged apps in our sample of 30 malware remove the method `void b(Context)` from the class `com.game.a`. This class extensively use the Android reflection API. Although it is not clear the real purpose of removing these methods, that decision simplifies the procedure of downloading a `data.apk` asset that is different from the asset available in the original version of the apps. Removing those methods might also be an strategy for antivirus evasion. For instance, although some usages of the class `DexClassLoader` might be legitimate, it allows specific types of attack based on dynamic code injection [48]. As such, antivirus might flag specific patterns using the Android reflection API suspect. Unfortunately, the also fails to identify a malicious behavior with this type of change (i.e., changes that remove methods). Listing 5 shows an example of code pattern frequently removed from the repackaged versions from the family.

In summary, our reverse engineering effort brings evidence that malware samples from the family neither modify the Android Manifest files nor call additional sensitive APIs. It acts as a downloader for further malicious app [49]—which reduce the ability of the to correctly classify a sample as a malware. Both versions (original/repackaged) from the family have the same behavior for showing advertisements to the user, however the repackaged version have additional call sites

Table 5. Summary of the outputs of the SimiDroid tool for the sample of 30 malware. (IM) Identical Methods, (SM) Similar Methods, (NM) New Methods, and (DM) Deleted Methods.

Hash	Family	IM	SM	NM	DM
33896E	0.9994	3205	2	0	0
0C962D	0.9994	3413	1	1	10
BCDF91	0.9992	2645	2	0	0
01ECE4	0.9991	5697	4	1	10
A306DA	0.9989	1886	1	1	6
4010CA	0.9987	3721	1	4	6
5B5F2D	0.9983	1164	2	3	0
010C07	0.9982	2248	4	3	0
F9FC04	0.9982	1121	1	1	6
E29F53	0.9976	842	1	1	6
FE76EB	0.9976	839	1	1	6
842BD5	0.9973	2249	3	3	3
295B66	0.9972	1081	2	1	10
92209D	0.9971	698	2	3	0
0977B0	0.9969	1613	4	1	10
347FCF	0.9967	613	1	1	6
00405B	0.9965	864	2	1	10
67310E	0.9957	1164	2	3	3
CCD29E	0.9954	436	2	0	0
610113	0.9941	836	4	1	10
A871E0	0.9941	836	4	1	10
ECEA10	0.9913	229	1	1	6
E53FAA	0.9889	267	2	1	10
723C23	0.9870	228	2	1	10
D95B6E	0.9870	833	10	1	10
17722D	0.9743	265	6	1	10
537492	0.9504	134	6	1	10
078E0A	0.9504	134	6	1	10
D83F1C	0.9494	150	2	6	6
E5D716	0.8840	2035	68	199	199

to the advertisement API and the advertisements sources are different. This behavior is not so harmful when compared to others repackaged apps, however nothing prevents that others malware families insert malicious operations, such as theft of sensitive data.

As the same way from samples, we also reengineer 30 samples from the family, choosed randomly, and which were not detected by the . As with the family samples, no instance from the family modified the Manifest file or inserted extra calls to sensitive APIs, making it harder for the to correctly label the samples as malware. However, our reverse engineering reveals that all apps store a file with the extension “.so” (Shared Object files) in their lib directory. These files are dynamic libraries containing native code written in C or C++, and are often

Table 6. Summary of the outputs of the SimiDroid tool for the sample of 30 malware. (IM) Identical Methods, (SM) Similar Methods, (NM) New Methods, and (DM) Deleted Methods.

Hash	Family	IM	SM	NM	DM
14BBE2	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
BFEF74	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
A3FACA	0.7918	2667	80	112	1 621
10F22D	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
50193A	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
5A7536	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
BCC0DB	0.7918	2667	80	112	1 621
E866CB	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
CDD316	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
DF39F6	0.7918	2667	80	112	1 621
3FFAFF	0.9121	3072	184	628	112
C8C63D	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
48C562	0.9121	3072	184	628	112
D27F26	0.7918	2667	80	112	1 621
F4BBEC	0.9121	3072	184	628	112
BCF14C	0.9127	3074	182	628	112
7FBF11	0.7918	2667	80	112	1 621
9D35D4	0.7918	2667	80	112	1 621
D1B27E	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
94DD4B	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
2D217E	0.7918	2667	80	112	1 621
66F167	0.7918	2667	80	112	1 621
155D4A	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
8CB780	0.9127	3074	82	628	112
C251FA	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
40487B	0.7918	2667	80	112	1 621
F29692	0.9940	3348	6	532	14
0E3679	0.9127	3074	182	628	112
7A4F31	0.9121	3072	184	628	112
BB3EDE	0.7105	2393	256	1217	719

used by apps for performance reasons, when resource-intensive tasks need to be performed [50].

Unfortunately, it is also possible to create malicious repackaged apps using “.so” files, as they can be replaced by a version containing harmful code [51]. The Shared Object files also allow for attacks based on dynamic code injection [48], considering that Android apps can use methods like `System.loadLibrary()` or `System.load()` to download malicious “.so” files from a remote server. Once on the device, malicious apps can use these files to interface with Java code in Android apps, via Java Native Code (JNI), performing malicious operations on low-level code, bypassing security mechanisms, like the .

Our assessment confirms that all of the samples contain Java code that loads a native library. To load these libraries, they use the `loadLibrary` method of the

`System` class, which is called in the static constructor of the `mainActivity` class. The `loadLibrary` method takes “game” as an argument, and the code automatically searches the default lib directory for the .so file named (`lib+argument`). In all samples, the “lib” directory contains the `libgame.so` file. Figure 6 present the code pattern of the `mainActivity` class found in the samples from family.

The `libgame.so` file contains compiled code written in C or C++, which is loaded into memory and linked to the apps at runtime. Although machine code is very difficult to analyze, we found that all the files include the `JNI_OnLoad` function, which JNI automatically uses to link Java methods and native functions. When we analyzed the hexadecimal “.so” file, we found that all of them differ in size and content between the original and repackaged apps. It is possible that changes of interest occurred in the native `libgame.so` file and have gone unnoticed by the .

5 Discussion

In this section, we answer our research questions, summarize the implications of our results, and discuss possible limitations of our study that might threaten the validity of the results presented so far.

5.1 Answers to the Research Questions

The results we presented in the previous sections allow us to answer our three research questions, as we summarize in the following.

- **Performance of the on the (RQ1).** Our study indicates that the accuracy of the reported in previous studies [5,9] does not generalize to a larger dataset. That is, while in our reproduction study (using the of previous research) the leads to an accuracy of , we observed a drop of precision and recall that leads to an accuracy of in the presence of our (pairs of original and repackaged versions of Android apps).
- **Similarity Analysis (RQ2).** Our results bring evidence about the existence of an association between the similarity of the original and repackaged versions of an app and the ability of the to correctly classify a repackaged version of an app as a malware. Therefore, the similarity assessment can explain the low performance of the to identify malware in the .
- **Malware Family Analysis (RQ3).** The results indicate that some families are responsible for the largest number of false negatives in the complete dataset. We specifically further investigate the and families, which corresponds to a particular type of Adwares, designed to automatically display advertisements while an app is running. After reverse engineering a sample of 60 malware apps from and family, we confirmed that the cannot identify the patterns of changes introduced in the repackaged versions of the apps. The prevalence of the and in the also contributed to explaining the poor performance of the for malware classification in the large dataset.

First, the proportion of malware samples in the datasets differs. That is, labels 66.95% of the repackaged version of the apps in the as malware—contrasting with 67.64% of the samples that labels as malware in the .

5.2 Implications

Contrasting to previous research works [5,6,9], our results lead to a more systematic understanding of the strengths and limitations of using the for malware classification. In particular, this is the first study that empirically evaluates the considering as ground truth the outcomes of . This decision allowed us to explore the performance using well-known accuracy metrics (i.e., precision, recall, and F_1 score). Previous studies assume that all repackaged versions of the apps were malware. Our triangulation with reveals this is not true. Although the presents a good accuracy for the ($F_1 =$), in the presence of a large dataset the accuracy drops significantly ($F_1 =$).

We also reveal that some families in the are responsible for a large number of false negatives, compromising the accuracy of the . Altogether, the takeaways of this research are twofold:

- Negative result: the for malware detection exhibits a much higher false negative rate than previous research reported.
- Future directions: Researchers should advance the for malware detection by exploring more sophisticated techniques for differentiating between benign and malicious versions of apps. In particular, new approaches should leverage methods that can identify specific patterns of changes in repackaged versions and mine sensitive calls to native APIs. The versatility of the Java Native Interface (JNI) has introduced challenges, as malware authors are increasingly using the native layer to hide malicious code, making both static and dynamic analysis more challenging. The current state of the art in sandbox mining overlooks native calls.

5.3 Threats to Validity

There are some threats to the validity of our results. Regarding **external validity**, one concern relates to the representativeness of our malware datasets and how generic our findings are. Indeed, mitigating this threat was one of the motivations for our research, since, in the existing literature, researchers had explored just one dataset of 102 pairs of original/repackaged apps. Curiously, for this small dataset, the performance of the is substantially superior than its performance on our (pairs of apps).

We contacted the authors of the Bao et al. research paper [5], asking them if they had used any additional criteria for selecting the pairs of apps in their dataset. Their answers suggest the contrary: they have not used any particular app selection process that could explain the superior performance of the for the . We believe that our results in the generalize better than previous research work,

since we have a more comprehensive collection of malware with different families and degrees of similarity. Nonetheless, our research focus only on Android repackaged malware and thus we cannot generalize our findings to malware that targets other platforms or that use different approaches to instantiate a malicious asset. Besides that, repackaging is a recurrent approach for implementing Android malware.

Regarding **conclusion validity**, during the exploratory phase of the , we collected the set of calls to sensitive APIs the original version of an app executes, while running a test case generation tool (DroidBot). That is, the assumes the existence of a benign original version of a given app in the exploratory phase. We also query to confirm this assumption, and found that the original version of seven (out 102) apps in the contains malicious code. We believe the authors of previous studies carefully check that assumption, and this difference had occurred because the outputs of change over time [39], and a dataset that is consistent at a date will not so in the future. Therefore, while reproducing this research, it is necessary to query to get the most up-to-date classification of the assets, which might lead to results that might slightly diverge from what we have reported here. Besides that, in the we only consider pairs of original/repackaged apps for which classifies the original version as benign.

Regarding the **correlation between dataset properties and accuracy drop**, after running statistical tests (logistic regression), we could not find evidence that the *diversity* of the complete dataset—in terms of similarity score and types of malware- is responsible for the higher number of false negatives of the mining sandbox approach. This implies that there was no 1-1 correlation between the brackets of similarity index, malware types to the drops in accuracy. Therefore, further research is necessary to investigate other possible reasons for that. Perhaps, the complete dataset contains a large percentage of malware that use more advanced techniques to evade from both static and dynamic analysis—both methods are used in the mining sandbox approach we discussed in this paper.

Regarding **construct validity**, we address the main threats to our study by using simple and well-defined metrics that are in use for this type of research: number of malware samples the correctly/wrongly classify in a dataset (true positives/false negatives). Based on these metrics, we computed the accuracy results using precision and recall. In a preliminary study, we investigated whether or not the would classify an original version of an app as a malware, computing the results of the test case generation tools in multiple runs. After combining three executions in an original version to build a sandbox, we did not find any other execution that could wrongly label an original app as a malware. Also, we label a repackaged version of an app as malware only if reports that at least two engines detect suspicious behavior in that asset. This decision might be viewed as either a weak or strong constraint and could raise concerns about construct validity. However, when we relax this constraint and label an asset as malware whenever at least one engine detects suspicious behavior, precision improves to 0.85, but recall drops to 0.39. Overall, the accuracy of the remains almost

unchanged ($F_1 = 0.53$)—still significantly lower than the precision of the for . We also evaluated accuracy by considering an asset as malware when at least five or ten VirusTotal security engines flagged it. As shown in Table 7, the results did not diverge significantly.

Table 7. Accuracy of the at (4,076 pairs) based on engines.

Engine(s)	TP	FP	FN	Precision	Recall	F_1
At least 01	1,222	220	1,900	0.85	0.39	0.53
At least 02	1,175	220	1,720	0.84	0.40	0.54
At least 05	1,087	220	1,578	0.83	0.40	0.54
At least 10	1,002	220	1,469	0.81	0.40	0.54

6 Conclusions

To better understand the strengths and limitations of the for repackaged malware detection, this paper reported the results of an empirical study that reproduces previous research works [5,9] using a more diverse dataset—in comparison to the datasets used in previous research. To our surprise, compared to published results, the performance of the drops significantly for our comprehensive dataset (F_1 score reduces from 0.89 in previous papers to 0.54 here). This result is partially explained by the high prevalence of a specific malware families (named and), whose samples are incorrectly classified by the . We also report the results of a reverse engineering effort, whose goal was to understand the features from the and family that reduce the performance of the for malware classification. Our reverse engineering effort revealed common changing patterns in the repackaged versions of original apps, which mostly use reflection to download an external apk asset for handling advertisements without introducing additional calls to sensitive APIs. Similarly, the family does not include any additional calls to sensitive resources, however it often uses JNI to interact with native code, which can be used to perform malicious operations at a low level, compromising the effectiveness of the for malware identification. These negative results highlight the current limitations of the MAS approach for malware classification and suggest the need for further research to integrate the MAS approach with other techniques for more effective malware identification.

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Data Availability

The datasets used and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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(a) for the samples in the family.

(b) for the samples in the family.

Fig. 3. Histogram of the for the samples in the and families.

```

public void onReceive(Context context, Intent intent) {
    SharedPreferences sp = context.getSharedPreferences("com."+ "game." + "param", 0);
    int i = sp.getInt("sn", 0) + 1;
    System.out.println("sn: " + i);
    if (i < 2) {
        mo4a(context);
        SharedPreferences.Editor edit = sp.edit();
        edit.putInt("sn", i);
        edit.commit();
    } else if (!new C0004b(context).f7h.equals("")) {
        String str1 = context.getApplicationInfo().dataDir;
        String str2 = String.valueOf(str1) + "/fi" + "les/d" + "ata.a" + "pk";
        String str3 = String.valueOf(str1) + "/files";
        String str4 = String.valueOf("com.") + "ccx." + "xm." + "SDKS" + "tart";
        String str5 = String.valueOf(" InitS") + "tart";
        String str6 = "ff048a5de4cc5eabec4a209293513b6e";
        C0003a.m3a(context, str2, str3, str4, str5, str6);
        SharedPreferences.Editor edit2 = sp.edit();
        edit2.putInt("sn", 0);
        edit2.commit();
    }
}

```

Fig. 4. Method introduced in 29 out of 30 malware we randomly selected from the .

```

public static void m7a(Activity activity, String str, String str2, ... , String str5) {
    try {
        Class loadClass = new DexClassLoader(..., activity.getClassLoader()).loadClass(str3);
        Object newInstance = loadClass.getConstructor(new Class[0]).newInstance(new Object[0]);
        Method method = loadClass.getMethod(str4, new Class[] { Activity.class, String.class });
        method.setAccessible(true);
        method.invoke(newInstance, new Object[] { activity, str5 });
    } catch (Exception e) {
        e.printStackTrace();
    }
}

```

Fig. 5. Example of method that is typically removed from the repackaged apps of the family.

```

public class PZPlayer extends Cocos2dxActivity {
    // ...
    System.loadLibrary("game");
    // ...
}

```

Fig. 6. This code links this java file into libgame shared library